

Spatial Conceptual Metaphors in English Literary Texts

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Abstract: This article explores the role of spatial metaphors in shaping human cognition and understanding, building on Lakoff and Johnson's theory of conceptual metaphor. It argues that metaphors are fundamental not only in language but also in structuring abstract concepts like emotions, time, and morality. Through the lens of spatial metaphors such as "up-down," "in-out," and "front-back," the paper examines how abstract ideas are grounded in physical experiences. Key studies by Boroditsky, Casasanto, and Meier and Robinson highlight cultural, bodily, and emotional influences on metaphor use. Additionally, the article analyzes spatial metaphors in O. Henry's short stories, demonstrating how they enhance narrative depth and convey complex themes such as social status, moral change, and emotional states. The paper underscores the cognitive and rhetorical power of spatial metaphors in both everyday language and literary expression.

Keywords: conceptual metaphors, spatial conceptual metaphor, abstract concepts, cross-linguistic perspective, emotional state.

INTRODUCTION. A conceptual metaphor is a cognitive framework that shapes how we understand and reason about abstract concepts by mapping them onto more concrete, familiar experiences. This theory was first extensively developed by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson in their seminal work *Metaphors We Live By* (1980). According to their theory, metaphors are not just linguistic expressions or poetic flourishes, but fundamental to human thought. They help structure our understanding of the world and guide our reasoning. There are three types conceptual metaphors including spatial conceptual metaphors, structural and ontological metaphors.

Lakoff and Johnson's theory of conceptual metaphor, presented in their book "Metaphors We Live By" (1980), argues that metaphors are not just linguistic expressions but fundamental to how humans think and understand the world. According to their theory, abstract concepts—such as emotions, time, morality, and social relationships—are understood through metaphors that map them onto concrete, physical experiences rooted in our everyday bodily interactions. For example, happiness is metaphorically conceptualized as **up** ("I'm feeling up"), and sadness as **down** ("feeling low").

In their book *Where Mathematics Comes From* (2000), Lakoff and Núñez expanded the scope of spatial metaphors by exploring how mathematical concepts, often considered abstract, rely on spatial metaphors. They argued that "**more is up**" (e.g., "prices are rising") and "**addition is putting together**" (e.g., "stacking numbers") are spatial metaphors that structure mathematical thought. Their research showed that even abstract, formal fields

like mathematics are deeply influenced by spatial metaphors, further supporting the idea that these metaphors are central to cognition.

Lera Boroditsky's study (*Cognitive Psychology*, 2001) on how different cultures conceptualize time using spatial metaphors provided a cross-linguistic perspective. She found that English speakers tend to use horizontal metaphors for time (e.g., "looking forward to the future"), while Mandarin speakers also use vertical metaphors (e.g., "the next month is down"). Her experiments demonstrated that speakers of different languages are influenced by the spatial metaphors prevalent in their culture, affecting how they think about time. Boroditsky's work supports the hypothesis of linguistic relativity, showing that language can shape thought, particularly through spatial metaphors. She showed Cross-linguistic differences in spatial metaphors which reveal that cultural factors influence how abstract domains like time are conceptualized.

Daniel Casasanto (2009) proposed the **Body-Specificity Hypothesis**, arguing that people's bodily experiences influence their spatial metaphors. For example, right-handed people tend to associate **right** with positive concepts, while left-handed people associate **left** with positivity. This study demonstrated that spatial conceptual metaphors are not only shaped by universal human experiences (as Lakoff and Johnson suggested) but are also influenced by individual bodily characteristics. This research provided a nuanced understanding of how personal physical experiences contribute to the creation and variation of spatial metaphors.

Meier and Robinson's research (*Psychological Science*, 2004) focused on the relationship between spatial metaphors and emotional states, particularly the **up-down** metaphor. Their experiments showed that individuals are faster to identify positive words when they are presented at the top of a screen and negative words at the bottom, reflecting the **up is good, down is bad** metaphor. This study provided empirical support for the claim that spatial metaphors, especially those related to emotions, are deeply embedded in cognitive processing and influence perception.

In his analysis of political discourse, Crawford (2009) explored how spatial metaphors are used to frame political ideologies and decisions. He found that metaphors such as **moving forward** (progress) and **falling behind** (regression) are frequently employed in political speeches to evoke emotional responses and justify policies. By mapping political ideas onto spatial metaphors, politicians can make abstract policies more relatable and persuasive to the public. Crawford's study highlights the rhetorical power of spatial metaphors in shaping public opinion and political thought.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS. Metaphors consist of two domains including the source domain which is the concrete, physical experience (e.g., "up," "money") , and the target domain which is the abstract concept being described (e.g., "happiness," "time"). Metaphors create a mapping between these domains, allowing us to understand the abstract through the concrete.

Thus, metaphors are a cognitive tool that helps us grasp complex, abstract ideas by relating them to concrete, familiar experiences. This theory shifts the view of metaphors from merely decorative language to a core aspect of human thinking and understanding.

Spatial conceptual metaphors are metaphors that rely on spatial orientation—such as “up-down”, “in-out”, “front-back”, and similar directions—to conceptualize and understand abstract ideas. These metaphors use our physical experiences of space and movement to frame complex, intangible concepts like emotions, social status, morality, or time. Time is often conceptualized spatially by explaining **future is ahead** such as "Looking forward to tomorrow" and **past is behind** ("Leave the past behind"). Besides, emotions can be spatially conceptualized by using spatial preposition “**up**” for happiness ("I'm on cloud nine", "I am

feeling up”) and **“down”** for sadness (“I hit rock bottom”, I am feeling down). Additionally, people’s morality can be framed in spatial terms by using **high** for moral superiority: “He’s upstanding” and **low** for moral inferiority: “He’s fallen into disgrace.”. Also social status among people can be framed by using low and high.

HIGH STATUS IS UP	LOW STATUS IS DOWN
<p>He has a lofty position.</p> <p>She'll rise to the top.</p> <p>He's at the peak of his career.</p> <p>He's climbing the ladder.</p> <p>He has little upward mobility</p>	<p>He's at the bottom of the social hierarchy.</p> <p>She fell in status</p>

It should be admitted that **“up”** is often associated with positive concepts (e.g., happiness: “I’m feeling up”) while **“down”** is linked to negative ones (e.g., sadness: “I’m feeling down”). **“In”** can represent inclusion or safety (e.g., “being in the group”), while **“out”** signifies exclusion or danger (e.g., “left out”). **Forward** often represents progress or the future (e.g., “looking forward”), whilst **“back”** symbolizes regression or the past (e.g., “stuck in the past”). These metaphors draw on our embodied experience of physical space to make abstract ideas more comprehensible by grounding them in familiar spatial relationships.

Conceptual metaphors are used not only in oral speech, but writers also use such metaphors in order to convey abstract themes and emotions more understandable in literary texts. In this article, there are some examples and interpretations of spatial conceptual metaphors in O.Henry’s short stories. O.Henry, known for his witty, ironic short stories and unexpected plot twists, often employs spatial conceptual metaphors to enhance the emotional depth, themes, and narrative structure of his works. These metaphors help illustrate abstract ideas like social status, morality, and emotional states by linking them to familiar spatial relationships such as up-down, in-out, and front-back. In his famous short story called “The Last Leaf”, Johnsy, a young woman who is gravely ill with pneumonia, links her life to the last leaf on a vine outside her window. As the leaves fall, she feels her life ebbing away, and she imagines that when the last leaf falls, she will die. The metaphor of falling (downward movement) is closely tied to her declining health and loss of hope. Another illustration is that, the painter Behrman, who eventually paints the final leaf to give Johnsy hope, metaphorically represents an upward movement toward life and hope, counteracting the downward metaphor of death and despair.

The short story called “The Furnished Room” centers on a man searching for his lost love in a rented room, which is described as suffocating and “stifling,” evoking a sense of being trapped or sinking into despair. The downward metaphor here represents the character’s mental and emotional descent, as he loses hope and ultimately succumbs to despair by committing suicide. The enclosed, low-ceilinged, and oppressive space of the room physically mirrors his fall into isolation and loss.

In the short story named “The Cop and the Anthem”, Soapy, a homeless man in New York, desperately tries to get arrested so that he can spend the winter inside the warm confines of jail. His repeated failures to get arrested represent his inability to find belonging or inclusion in society. The concept of in and out is central to the plot, where Soapy views jail as a form of inclusion and security (inside) versus the outside world, which leaves him cold, hungry, and homeless. The metaphor of being in jail here is paradoxically positive, as it represents safety and warmth, whereas being out in the streets is associated with exclusion, rejection, and vulnerability.

If we analyze the short story called "The Skylight Room" by O'Henry, the spatial metaphor of upward movement is evident in this story, where Miss Leeson, a poor typist, rents the cheapest room in a boarding house—a tiny "skylight room" at the top of the building. While the upward space might traditionally represent elevation or hope, O. Henry uses the irony that this tiny, cramped room represents Miss Leeson's struggle with poverty. Instead of an elevated status, the room symbolizes her isolation and exclusion from the affluent world below. The "skylight" offers a false sense of connection to the outside world, reinforcing her feeling of being trapped in her circumstances.

In the story called "After Twenty Years" which is about two old friends who meet after twenty years, the metaphor of front and back reflects the passage of time and the divergence of their lives. The character of Jimmy, who has become a law-abiding policeman, is metaphorically moving forward, having progressed in life. In contrast, his old friend Bob has metaphorically fallen back into a life of crime, as he is eventually arrested at the end of the story. The spatial metaphor of looking forward to the future versus being pulled back by the past plays a key role in this story. Bob's failure to move forward morally has consequences, while Jimmy, who has followed a straight and lawful path, represents the forward movement toward stability.

In the story named after "A Retrieved Reformation" we can see "center-periphery" metaphors. In this story, Jimmy Valentine, a safecracker, reforms his ways after falling in love. However, when his criminal past threatens to be exposed, the story uses a center-periphery metaphor to highlight his transformation. When he is on the "periphery" of society as a criminal, Jimmy exists in the margins, excluded from legitimate society. His decision to go into the center both morally and socially—by taking on an honest life is represented through his integration into the community and his pursuit of a respectable identity. The literal and metaphorical movement toward the center of society, through his new identity as Ralph D. Spencer, contrasts with his previous life on the outskirts as a criminal.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the theory of conceptual metaphors, as articulated by Lakoff and Johnson, reveals that our understanding of abstract concepts is intricately shaped by metaphors that map these ideas onto our physical experiences. Spatial metaphors, in particular, offer a powerful framework for conceptualizing complex ideas such as emotions, time, morality, and social status. The research of scholars like Boroditsky, Casasanto, and Meier and Robinson has expanded our understanding of how these metaphors vary across cultures and personal experiences, emphasizing that spatial metaphors are not only a universal feature of human cognition but are also influenced by individual and cultural differences. Furthermore, the use of spatial metaphors in literature, as seen in O. Henry's short stories, demonstrates their capacity to enrich narrative and deepen emotional resonance, reflecting the profound connection between language, thought, and lived experience. Ultimately, spatial metaphors serve as a bridge between the tangible and the intangible, making abstract concepts more accessible and comprehensible.

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